

To what Degree are African Researchers Publishing in Open Access Journals Since the launch of Plan S

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Digital Disruption in #HigherEd

□ Rise & demand for

□ **OA**> seeks to return scholarly publishing to its original purpose: spread knowledge and allow it to be freely accessible.

□ No paywalls

Global Trends in OA

Plan S

Making full and
immediate Open
Access a reality

- ❑ Launched in 2018
- ❑ Supported by a cOAlition S, an international consortium of research funders.
- ❑ Requires that, from 2021, scientific publications that result from research funded by public grants must be published in compliant Open Access journals or platforms.

Open Access Publications 2018-Date

(As of 4 Aug)

☐ > 310,694 publications

Open Access 47.5 %

☐ Medical & Health Research > 66,048

☐ Visual Arts & Crafts > 11

Total Publication output trends year on year

All years: 147,515

Show years 2011 to 2020

Chart | Table

Citation impact Non OA VS OA

163,179-Publications

Citations
362 K

Citations (Mean)
2.22

Name	↓ Publications	Citations
All OA	147,515	369,497
Pure Gold	70,385	166,416
Bronze	33,490	61,079
Hybrid	18,544	58,158
Green, Published	11,513	23,209
Green, Submitted	9,682	31,560
Green, Accepted	3,901	29,075

OA Paper with highest Altmetric Score

MO

Mentioned by

- 546 news outlets
- 69 blogs
- 2 policy sources
- 8252 tweeters
- 54 Facebook pages
- 12 Wikipedia pages
- 18 Redditors
- 1 research highlight platform
- 1 video uploader

Citations

- 65 Dimensions

Readers on

- 848 Mendeley

World Scientists' Warning of a Climate Emergency

Overview of attention for article published in BioScience, November 2019

SUMMARY

News

Blogs

Policy documents

Title	World Scientists' Warning of a Climate Emergency
Published in	BioScience, November 2019
DOI	10.1093/biosci/biz088 ↗
Authors	William J Ripple, Christopher Wolf, Thomas M Newsome, Phoebe Bar...

TWITTER DEMOGRAPHICS

MENDELEY

Non OA Paper with highest Altmetric Score

Top 15 OA Journals Africans are publishing

Research Square		5,087	
PLoS ONE		3,111	
SSRN Electronic Journal		2,152	
bioRxiv		1,894	
Scientific Reports		1,459	
Pan African Medical Journal		1,431	6
RSC Advances		1,071	
Journal of Physics Conference Series		1,013	
IOP Conference Series Materials Science an...		929	
BMC Public Health		910	
IEEE Access		828	
Heliyon		811	
BMC Research Notes		776	
South African Medical Journal		739	14
The Medical Journal of Cairo University		696	15

Top Funders?

- ❑ European Commission- 3,381
- ❑ Wellcome Trust- 2,861
- ❑ National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases- 2,792
- ❑ Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation -2,453
- ❑ Medical Research Council, UK -2,330
- ❑ National Natural Science Foundation of China - 2,075
- ❑ European Research Council -1,494
- ❑ German Research Foundation-1,457
- ❑ World Health Organization- 1,424
- ❑ National Institute of Mental Health-1,183
- ❑ National Institute of Child Health and Human Development-1,136
- ❑ South African Medical Research Council -1,074 (12TH)

DATA COURTESY OF DIMENSIONS.AI

Conclusion

- ❑ African researchers have by 47.5%
- ❑ Strong correlation with citation impact and open access publications
- ❑ Strong correlation with increased research visibility in open access publications- altmetric score
- ❑ Kenyan journal is leading in open access publication
- ❑ Top funders - **South African Medical Research Council -1,074 is 12th .**

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improving research output & visibility

• Rectangular Snip

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We are an award-winning, 14-year old Trust, in partnership with University of Nairobi, Kenya and the first African-based training centre to teach effective communication skills to scientists.

Abstract

This dissertation reports a study on the degree-of-freedom systems with particular sources of energy dissipation which

E-Resources for Research

Science communication and Communicating to Non Scientist

Oral communication and presentation

Resource Mobilization and Grants Management

Data Analysis for Presentation

Scientific Writing and Publishing

